

To Preprint or Not to Preprint?

An Interview with KU Leuven Researchers on
the Advantages and Disadvantages
of Preprint Publishing

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Preprints are gaining more and more popularity. The main motivation behind releasing a preprint is to already share your research findings before submitting your manuscript to a journal. While in some fields publishing preprints has become standard practice, some researchers are still reluctant. We have asked six KU Leuven researchers how they feel about preprints and how preprint servers relate to the traditional publication system.

Why do you choose to submit papers to a preprint server?

Laure: I use preprint servers for three main reasons. In the first place, preprints make it possible to quickly share time-sensitive results. Especially in times of health emergencies, such as the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus, they allow you to immediately share new scientific findings. Secondly, I find open peer review to be very valuable as it offers transparency and participation. Thirdly, by publishing a preprint you create a public record of your work: by openly sharing your research results you can let other scholars know that you are working on a certain topic.

Ines: Thanks to preprints we can indeed engage much earlier in scientific discussions and can share our work and approaches faster with the community, our network and potential other stakeholders. Mainly when the work is embedded in bigger projects this provides a huge benefit, as preprints enable you to increase collaborations in the context of ongoing research. This is in contrast with the traditional publication system, where papers often only get published after the project has ended.

Jeroen: The main reason why I submit preprints is to make my work more easily detectable. The fact that preprints can help to get your work out as fast as possible is less important in my field, since for us conference proceedings are a popular medium and they have a shorter revision period than traditional journals.

Kaat: Also important to highlight is that preprint servers form a crucial step in the Open Science movement that aims at making science available to the broader public. A great advantage lies in the fact that preprints allow making research data public without depending on the timeline of journals' editorial boards and review processes.

Ben: I fully agree with Kaat, one of the great things about preprints is that they are accessible by everyone all over the world, also by people who don't have access to paywalled journals. A very good technical feature we should also mention is that the preprint gets a DOI which makes it easy to cite. This is especially interesting if a paper is not yet accepted by a traditional journal and you wish to submit new work that builds further on the paper under review.

Jean-Jacques: I can only confirm what my colleagues have already highlighted: immediate and free access without the delay of peer review (which can take up to 9 months!). What is also interesting is that you can receive feedback from peers outside of the official peer-review system. A final thing I want to point out is that preprints are devoid of journal prestige. All preprints are equal in terms of prestige because they are not published in a specific journal yet, where different journals are associated with different prestige. The scientific work contained in a preprint has to

be judged on its own merit, not on the brand of the journal where it is published. This is appealing to me because it removes an important bias in how we judge papers.

Do you believe that submitting preprints helps to increase the impact and visibility of your work?

Jeroen: While doing a PhD, I believe you should make your work as visible as possible, not only by submitting to preprint servers but also by attending conferences and by using social media. It has occurred to me that I felt that I should have been cited in someone else's paper but it is understandable with the huge amount of academic work out there that my paper had been missed. Preprints offer the opportunity to enhance the visibility of my research, which in turn leads to more citations.

Jean-Jacques: Absolutely, preprints are easily shared online via social media and are immediately accessible to everybody as they are available much faster than papers published via the traditional publishing system. Research has shown that papers first published as a preprint and later on submitted to a journal attract more citations and more online visibility (see studies on [eLife](#) and [bioRxiv](#)).

Kaat: Moreover, having your work published as a preprint makes it possible to reference to this prior work in grant applications. At times this can be crucial, e.g. for demonstrating the lab's expertise or experience with a particular methodology or conceptual topic. Also for young researchers, who are in between PhD and post-doc, it can be important to cite all the work that they have accomplished during their PhD in order to be competitive for post-doctoral fellowship applications. This is facilitated by preprint servers.

Ines: I have been contacted multiple times about a preprint by international colleagues, both inside and outside academia, so I'm very sure that preprints increase the visibility of my research. The fact that you can freely share the link with others, without the restrictions of a paywall, is a great advantage. I also myself regularly check bioRxiv for newly added work of my network or within my research interests.

Laure: Although I don't think that preprints enhance the impact of my work, as impact is determined by quality, I do believe they help to increase the visibility. For example, a preprint that we published about Covid-19 at the end of March received more than 4.000 full text downloads in a few weeks' time.

Do you think that the preprint version of your paper is sufficient or do you still prefer to also publish your paper in a "traditional" journal?

Ben: At our research unit we always have the intention to also get the work published in a peer-reviewed journal. The work gets extra exposure through the journal and publications in peer-reviewed journals are valued much more in the evaluation of project applications. But in the meantime, the work is already available as a preprint during the reviewing process, which can

take several months. I also have the impression that our peer-reviewed papers are picked up sooner if the work is already introduced via a preprint.

Ines: Since the academic system is often based on winning external funding, publishing in high-impact journals remains important. Moreover, we publish because we want to show our work to an international community, therefore, getting it accepted in a specific journal helps to reach your targeted audience. Another aspect is the added value of peer review. Although it can be time-consuming, it remains helpful to get feedback from your peers about the scientific quality of your work.

Jeroen: Personally, I also still prefer to publish my paper in a peer-reviewed journal or conference proceeding, as preprints are not valorized in the current academic evaluation system. Furthermore, as Ines already mentioned, I find the comments of reviewers to be very valuable.

Kaat: My colleagues have already pointed out the main issue: in the current academic system researchers are required to disseminate their work in established journals, preferably in one that is high-ranked and with a high impact factor, in order to be competitive for attracting funding and positions. If we don't change the evaluation system researchers will be required to continue publishing their work in traditional journals.

How do you feel about initiatives such as ['Peer Community in'](#) that aim at valorizing preprints?

Jean-Jacques: I think the current publishing model is broken and costs too much money. I believe that peer review should still happen at some point but we have to explore innovative publishing models. More and more journals are also allowing you to directly submit your paper from a preprint server to a journal, which speeds up the process. eLife even encourages its authors to post their research as a preprint, either before submission or during the review process.

Kaat: I agree, we have to examine new ways of publishing scientific output. One could envisage an evolution in the publishing field, in which the role of the journal itself is gradually diminished and the role of preprint servers or similar initiatives becomes more important. For example, if only the number of citations is considered as a publication metric, then this could also be obtained based on preprints alone. Nevertheless, it will still be necessary, or at least desirable, to gain some a priori assessment of the quality of submitted work, which is increasingly difficult without peer review. In this respect, initiatives such as Peer Community in (PCI) may provide a valuable solution. I look forward to see how this community expands in the future.

Ben: The concept of PCI is really interesting, but if your final goal is still to also get the work published in a traditional peer-reviewed journal, then PCI is just an additional step in the process requiring extra work, at least for now. I believe that further advancement of this platform will result in a more efficient flow from preprint to peer-reviewed publication. So, we are not making use of PCI now, but I am sure that we will in the future.

Ines: I am really convinced of the concept of PCI. Especially open peer review is very valuable and I am curious to see how this platform will evolve. Another interesting initiative is preLights, it

offers a way of engaging with authors about non-peer reviewed work, providing both valuable comments and more visibility. In the future the need to publish in traditional journals might decrease if the research community makes more and more use of these alternative platforms to share their work.

Do you see any disadvantages about submitting preprints?

Ben: A disadvantage that is often put forward is that journals don't accept papers that have already been published as a preprint. However, as far as I know, all the scientific journals in which we publish accept papers that have been submitted to a preprint server first. A technical feature that can be improved is establishing a stable link between the preprint and the peer-reviewed article to indicate more clearly that they are both about the same work, experiments and research.

Laure: While preprints can be published quicker than peer-reviewed articles it could go even faster, as it takes approximately 5 days to publish a preprint which is still too long during health crises when the situation is evolving rapidly. I also want to point out that we should be cautious of preprints of a very low quality, which can distract our attention from the good quality papers that you can find on preprint servers.

Jean-Jacques: The Covid-19 pandemic has shown us that there is a need to educate people about what preprints are. Some preprints were picked up by the media and spread as containing proven facts, which is highly problematic. We should not consider preprints as absolute truths but more as a proposed set of results that require further scrutiny by experts. I would argue that this is actually also the case for papers that pass peer review, as peer review is not perfect either. Further debate is necessary: what do we do if a preprint has later been found to contain mistakes? Can a preprint be retracted?

Ben: Yes, I also have the impression that the concept of preprints and the legal aspects are not always clear, even for fellow researchers. We should invest in explaining why and how you can use preprint servers so that the reach of this platform can increase more and more in the coming years.

To the final question if they would recommend colleagues to submit to preprint servers all six unanimously answered YES! While preprint servers have their own issues, mainly the lack of quality control, they offer many advantages: rapid dissemination, enhanced visibility, Open Access and increased collaboration.

We would like to thank all six researchers for sharing their valuable insights about preprints!

Meet the interviewees

Ines Adriaens holds a postdoc position in the lab of Livestock Technology. After her PhD defense in November 2018, she decided to remain in research interfacing academia and the industry, in which she develops (big) data solutions for dairy cows, combining biological knowledge with advanced data processing techniques. She vastly believes in open and transparent peer-evaluated research.

Ben Aernouts is Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Engineering Technology. He leads a research group working on Livestock Technology, where the focus is on the development, implementation and validation of innovative sensor technology and data-processing algorithms to support the animal management in livestock production. He has published multiple preprints on bioRxiv.

Kaat Alaerts is Assistant Professor at the department of Rehabilitation Sciences. She recently initiated an independent research program focused on the development of targeted neuromodulation approaches to facilitate neuroplastic changes in neurotypicals and neuropsychiatric populations. She also founded the Neuromodulation laboratory. She encourages all her lab members to submit their work as a preprint prior to, or in parallel with, submitting to a traditional journal.

Jean-Jacques Orban de Xivry is an engineer and Associate Professor working on movement neuroscience in the department of Movement Sciences. His projects focus on the effect of aging and neurological disease on motor control and learning via a multimodal approach (behavior, brain stimulation and neuroimaging). He is a strong supporter of Open Science: all papers are first published as preprints, all data and code are made openly available and studies are pre-registered when possible.

Laure Wynants is Assistant Professor at Maastricht University (Department of Epidemiology) and Postdoctoral Fellow at KU Leuven (Department of Development and Regeneration). Her main research interest are clinical prediction models, which are mathematical tools that assist doctors in making a diagnosis or prognosis. Recently she did a systematic review of all preprints about diagnostic and prognostic models for Covid-19.

Jeroen Zegers received his master in Electrical Engineering in 2010 at KU Leuven and started his PhD at the electrical engineering department in the same year. The goal of his thesis is to automatically distinguish and model speakers when their speech overlaps (simultaneous or overlapping speech). Most of his papers can be found on preprints servers, which is strongly recommended in his research group.